

Synthesis of Chromones. Part I. Condensation of Halogenated Phenols and Cresols with Alkyl Acetoacetic Esters.

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It has been shown by the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 129, 407) that polyhydroxy phenols and α -naphthol readily react with ethyl acetoacetates in presence of sulphuric acid or phosphorus pentoxide to give 1:2-pyrones or coumarins, the latter condensing agent not favouring the formation of 1:4-pyrones or chromones in those cases, as was expected from the experiments of Simonis and his collaborators (*Ber.*, 1913, 46, 2015; 1914, 47, 697, 2229; 1917, 50, 1142). The formation of coumarins with these phenols is instantaneous and is so general that it is difficult to change the course of the reaction even in the case of resorcinol-dimethylether which gives 7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin with the elimination of the methoxy group.

A perusal of the literature shows that the phenols differ greatly in their degree of readiness to form coumarins using sulphuric acid according to Pechmann. Of the cresols, while *o*-cresol does not react at all, *m*-cresol reacts most readily and the yield of the coumarin from *p*-cresol is not bad. The halogenated phenols respond to this reaction with reluctance, only traces of coumarins being formed (Clayton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 2018). It is however possible to change the course of this reaction with these phenols by the application of Simonis method using phosphorus pentoxide which yields chromones. In order to study the effect of substituents in ethyl acetoacetate on this reaction, the cresols and the halogenated phenols have been condensed with unsubstituted and substituted ethyl acetoacetates (the α -substituents being methyl, ethyl, propyl, isopropyl, isobutyl) with interesting results.

The halogenated phenols (*o*-, *p*-chloro- and *o*-, *p*-bromophenols) are by far the best in giving a comparatively good yield of the chromones but the generalisation made by Simonis, that the *o*-substituted phenols give a better yield, seems to be unwarranted. The

effect of the substituents in the acetoacetic ester molecule is not very marked in diminishing or increasing the yield, all giving chromones except ethyl- α -isobutylacetoacetate which gave resinous product from which nothing could be isolated. In the case of cresols it is found that *o*-cresol forms chromones with the alkyl acetoacetic esters with comparatively good yield; *p*-cresol gives a chromone when condensed with ethyl- α -methylacetoacetate but when the substituents are ethyl, propyl or isopropyl, no product can be isolated; *m*-cresol gives a coumarin with unsubstituted acetoacetic ester using both sulphuric acid and phosphorus pentoxide, but with ethyl- α -methylacetoacetate *m*-cresol gives a coumarin in poor yield using sulphuric acid (Kolestermann and Fries, *Annalen*, 1908, 362, 3) and a chromone using phosphorus pentoxide (Petschek and Simonis, *Ber.*, 1913, 46, 2014).

Simonis depended mainly on hydrolytic decomposition to establish the chromone structure of the compounds prepared by him; this often leads however to erroneous results (*cf.* Baker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2349) and in some cases, Simonis himself could not come to definite conclusion due to unsatisfactory hydrolysis. The chromone structure of all the compounds described here have been established by their condensation with aldehydes in presence of sodium ethoxide to form styrene derivatives. The chromones formed by the condensation of phenols with alkyl acetoacetic esters always contain a reactive methyl group in 2-position (*cf.* Heilbron, Barnes and Morton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2569) and are thus easily distinguished from 4-methylcoumarines as was previously pointed out by the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 131). The present investigation also proves that the reactivity of the 2-methyl group is not in any way influenced by the presence of a group (Cl, Br, or CH_3) in the benzene nucleus as is supposed by Heilbron and others.

EXPERIMENTAL.

General Method of the Preparation of the Halogenated Chromones.

A solution of the halogenated phenol (20 g.) in alkyl acetoacetic ester (19 g.) is slowly added with cooling to phosphorus pentoxide (45 g.) in a flask fitted with a calcium chloride tube, the mass being occasionally stirred. The mixture generally becomes hot and in some cases frothing takes place. After standing for fifteen minutes, it is gradually heated on the water-bath, when the

mass becomes pasty and the colour changes to red. The mixture is then thoroughly mixed and the heating continued for about three hours. The cold sticky product, thus obtained, is then treated with powdered ice and the viscous oil separating is extracted with ether. The ethereal extract is thoroughly washed with 5 p. c. caustic potash solution to remove the unchanged phenol and then with water to remove the alkali. On evaporating the ether a viscous semi-solid product is obtained, which sometimes gives beautiful crystals on washing with petroleum ether but generally, if the semi-solid mass is placed on a porous plate and left overnight, the coloured resinous substances are absorbed and colourless crystals are obtained. The product is finally crystallised from alcohol in a yield of 17 to 30 p. c.

General method of the preparation of the styrene derivatives by condensing the chromones with aldehydes.—An alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide is added to a solution of the aldehyde (1 mol.) and the chromone (1 mol.) in the minimum quantity of absolute alcohol, when the solution becomes warm. The solution, on keeping overnight, deposits crystals which are filtered off. A further crop of the crystals is also obtained by adding a few drops of water to the alcoholic mother-liquor. On recrystallisation from alcohol or acetic acid, well-defined crystals are obtained in almost quantitative yield.

Chromones from Chlorophenols.

8-Chloro-2-styryl-3-ethylchromone, obtained by the condensation of 8-chloro-2-methyl-3-ethylchromone (from *o*-chlorophenol and ethyl- α -ethylacetoacetate, Simonis and Schuhmann, *Ber.*, 1917, 50, 1142) with benzaldehyde, crystallises from rectified spirit in silky yellow needles melting at 137°. (Found: Cl, 11.7. $C_{19}H_{15}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 11.4 per cent.).

8-Chloro-2-methyl-3-propylchromone is obtained in 30 per cent. yield, from *o*-chlorophenol and ethyl- α -propylacetoacetate. It crystallises from alcohol as colourless needles, m.p. 100°. (Found: Cl, 14.72. $C_{13}H_{13}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 15.0 per cent.).

8-Chloro-2-styryl-3-propylchromone, the condensation product of 8-chloro-2-methyl-3-propylchromone with benzaldehyde, crystallises in needles from rectified spirit, m.p. 109°. (Found: Cl, 10.64. $C_{20}H_{17}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 10.9 per cent.).

8-Chloro-2-methyl-3-isopropylchromone is prepared by condensing *o*-chlorophenol with ethyl- α -isopropylacetoacetate. The reaction

starts only when heated; no appreciable change takes place in the cold. It crystallises in long shining needles melting at 160° from absolute alcohol. (Found: Cl, 15·3. $C_{13}H_{13}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 15·0 per cent.).

8-Chloro-2-styryl-3-isopropylchromone, the product obtained by reacting the above chromone with benzaldehyde, crystallises from rectified spirit in fine silky needles melting at 151°. (Found: Cl, 10·58. $C_{20}H_{17}O_2$ Cl requires Cl, 10·9 per cent.).

6-Chloro-2-styryl-3-methylchromone is prepared by the condensation of 6-chloro-2:3-dimethylchromone (from *p*-chlorophenol and ethyl- α -methylacetoacetate) with benzaldehyde. It crystallises from rectified spirit, m.p. 143°. (Found: Cl, 11·5. $C_{13}H_{13}O_2$ Cl requires Cl, 11·9 per cent.).

6-Chloro-2-methyl-3-propylchromone is obtained by condensing *p*-chlorophenol with ethyl- α -propylacetoacetate (the reaction starts in the cold with much rise of temperature). It crystallises from rectified spirit, m.p. 108°. (Found: Cl, 15·26. $C_{13}H_{13}O_2$ Cl requires Cl, 15·0 per cent.).

6-Chloro-2-styryl-3-propylchromone, the condensation product of 6-chloro-2-methyl-3-propylchromone with benzaldehyde, crystallises in needles from alcohol, m.p. 126°. (Found: Cl, 11·3. $C_{20}H_{17}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 10·9 per cent.).

6-Chloro-2-methyl-3-isopropylchromone, prepared from *p*-chlorophenol and ethyl- α -isopropylacetoacetate, crystallises from rectified spirit, m.p. 127°. (Found: Cl, 14·8. $C_{13}H_{13}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 15·0 per cent.).

6-Chloro-2-styryl-3-isopropylchromone, obtained by reacting the 6-chloro-2-methyl-3-isopropylchromone with benzaldehyde, crystallises in needles from rectified spirit, m.p., 159°. (Found: Cl, 11·3. $C_{20}H_{17}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 10·9 per cent.).

6:8-Dichloro-2-styryl-3-ethylchromone is prepared by condensing 6:8-dichloro-2-methyl-3-ethylchromone (from 2:4-dichlorophenol and ethyl- α -ethylacetoacetate) with benzaldehyde. It is crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 155-57°. (Found: Cl, 21·13. $C_{19}H_{14}O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 20·58 per cent.).

Chromones from Bromophenols.

8-Bromo-2-styryl-3-methylchromone, the product of the condensation of 8-bromo-2:3-dimethylchromone (from *o*-bromophenol and ethyl- α -methylacetoacetate) with benzaldehyde, crystallises from

absolute alcohol in silky yellow needles melting at 200°. (Found: Br, 23·71. $C_{18}H_{13}O_2Br$ requires Br, 23·46 per cent.).

8-Bromo-2-methyl-3-propylchromone, prepared from *o*-bromophenol and ethyl- α -propylacetoacetate, is crystallised from rectified spirit, m. p. 82°. (Found: Br, 28·12. $C_{13}H_{13}O_2Br$ requires Br, 28·4 per cent.).

6-Bromo-2-styryl-3-methylchromone, the product obtained by reacting 6-bromo-2:3-dimethylchromone (from *p*-bromophenol and ethyl- α -methylacetoacetate) with benzaldehyde, crystallises in yellow needles melting at 152° from absolute alcohol. (Found: Br, 23·1. $C_{13}H_{13}O_2Br$ requires Br, 23·46 per cent.).

6-Bromo-2-methyl-3-propylchromone, obtained from *p*-bromophenol and ethyl- α -propylacetoacetate, crystallises from dilute alcohol, m. p. 112°. (Found: Br, 28·5. $C_{13}H_{13}O_2Br$ requires Br, 28·4 per cent.).

6-Bromo-2-styryl-3-propylchromone, is crystallised from rectified spirit, m. p. 129°. (Found: Br, 21·2. $C_{20}H_{17}O_2Br$ requires Br, 21·6 per cent.).

Chromones from Cresols.

2-Styryl-3:6-dimethylchromone is obtained by condensing 2:3:6-trimethylchromone (from *p*-cresol and ethyl- α -methylacetoacetate, Petscheck and Simonis, *loc. cit.*) with benzaldehyde. It crystallises from rectified spirit as hard crystals melting at 120°. (Found: C, 82·48; H, 6·0. $C_{19}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 82·60; H, 5·8 per cent.).

3:4:6-Trimethylcoumarin, isomeric with 2:3:6-trimethylchromone is obtained by adding sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) in the cold to a solution of *p*-cresol (4 g.) in ethyl- α -methylacetoacetate (5 g.), keeping overnight and pouring the solution into water. It crystallises from dilute alcohol as colourless prisms, m. p. 165°, yield 5 g. (Found: C, 76·65; H, 6·48. $C_{12}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 76·6; H, 6·4 per cent.).

2-Styryl-3:8-dimethylchromone, prepared by reacting 2:3:8-trimethylchromone (from *o*-cresol with ethyl- α -methylacetoacetate, Petscheck and Simonis, *loc. cit.*) with benzaldehyde, crystallises as fine needles melting at 133° from rectified spirit. (Found: C, 82·55; H, 5·51. $C_{19}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 82·60; H, 5·8 per cent.).

2-(m-nitro-) styryl-3:8-dimethylchromone is produced by condensing 2:3:8-trimethylchromone with *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde. Silky needles (m. p. 225°) from glacial acetic acid. (Found: N, 4·56. $C_{19}H_{15}O_4N$ requires N, 4·36 per cent.).

2:8-Methyl-3-ethylchromone, prepared by the interaction of *o*-cresol with ethyl- α -ethylacetoacetate, crystallises from dilute alcohol, m.p. 71-72°. (Found: C, 77.1; H, 7.2. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 77.22; H, 6.9 per cent.).

2-Styryl-8-methyl-3-ethylchromone, the condensation product of the above chromone with benzaldehyde, crystallises from rectified spirit, m.p. 142°. (Found: C, 82.91; H, 6.05. $C_{20}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 82.75; H, 6.2 per cent.).

Coumarins from Resorcinol-mono- and dimethylether.

7-Methoxy-4-methylcoumarin.—(a) Resorcinol-monomethylether (5 g.) is condensed with ethyl acetoacetate (5 g.) with sulphuric acid (15 c.c.) in the cold. The reaction mixture, on keeping overnight, is poured into ice-cold water and the precipitate collected and crystallised as rhombic plates from dilute alcohol, m.p. 156-57°.

When phosphorus pentoxide (30 g.) is added in the cold to a solution of resorcinol-monomethylether (5 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (5.5 g.) vigorous reaction takes place. The mixture is poured into water and the solid collected and crystallised. It also melts at 156-57°, no depression of the melting point taking place when mixed with a specimen of the compound prepared with sulphuric acid or with a specimen of the methoxy derivative of β -methylumbelliferone.

(b) To a solution of resorcinol-dimethylether and ethyl acetoacetate sulphuric acid is added drop by drop at 0° (otherwise effervescence takes place and resinous products obtained). On keeping overnight and pouring into water a red solid is obtained. It is purified by heating on the water-bath with 10 p. c. caustic potash and acidifying. The precipitate, is collected, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 156-57°, no depression was observed when mixed with 7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin.

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